

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-*p*-Chloroaniline with Some Divalent Metal Ions

M. S. MAYADEO and S. H. HUSSAIN

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-400 019

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-chloroaniline. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 *M* in 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability of chelates is found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} > \text{Co} > \text{Mg}$ which is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams.

2-HYDROXY-1-naphthalidene-*p*-chloroaniline has been found to show phytohormonal properties¹. It has also been found to show biological activity in terms of the control of *staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *hay bacterium* and is reported to be one of the most active compounds².

The study of the interaction of this reagent with metal ions such as Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} etc. was thought to be interesting and hence, as such, a systematic study of the complexes of the reagent with some bivalent metal ions has been undertaken, as the same has not been reported in the literature.

This paper reports the stability constants of the chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-chloroaniline with some bivalent metal ions. The successive stability constants of the complexes have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

The Corning Model 12, a precision research *pH* meter was used for the *pH* measurements. The electrode assembly consisted of glass and calomel electrodes dipped into the titration mixture. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. Changes in *pH* can be determined with an accuracy of 0.005 *pH* unit.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-chloroaniline was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample (m.p. $158-159^\circ$)⁴.

The dioxan used for the experimental work was purified by the method described by Vogel⁵. Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium

permanganate and made free from carbon dioxide by boiling was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1 *M*). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared from AR grade metal salts and were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations⁶. All *pH* measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were prepared, the total volume in each case being 40 ml. These were then titrated potentiometrically against the standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (1.03 *M*).

(i) 5 ml of (0.16 *M*) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 *M*) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.

(ii) 5 ml of (0.16 *M*) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 *M*) NaClO_4 + a requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

(iii) 5 ml of (0.64 *M*) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.008 *M*) metal salt solution in (0.16 *M*) HClO_4 + a requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti³ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL .

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (*pH* meter readings) were

calculated and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.25 < \bar{n}_A < 1.31$ and is wavelike. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ while that of pK_2^H was obtained graphically by extrapolation.

Fig. 1. 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-*p*-Chloroaniline. Plot of 'B' (pH meter reading) against Volume of NaOH added, ml.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were evaluated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria. From these formation curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$, which correspond to the pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ were computed. In the present study the *bis*-complexes could not be studied because of precipitation. The limit of error for the $\log K$ values was found to be ± 0.05 and the standard deviation to be ± 0.067 .

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE-1 STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES.

Cations	$t = 25^\circ$					
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
Log K_1	9.30	7.26	5.07	5.00	5.66	3.32
Log K_2	2.11	-	-	-	-	-

For proton association (H^+), K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species LH and LH_2^+ respectively. Y , the total number of replaceable protons per ligand molecule, is 1. For metal ions K_1 corresponds to the species ML_1 .

The order of stability of the bivalent metal chelates was found to be $Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Mg$. The order is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams⁸.

In similarity with the observations made by Calvin and Melchior⁹ in the case of 5-salicylaldehyde-sulphonate, a correlation for the series Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with the second ionisation potential of the gaseous atoms was also observed in the present study. This can be graphically illustrated by plotting the stability constants and the ionisation potentials as a function of atomic number.

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